

Anxiety as Correlate of Academic Performance Among Secondary School Students in Ogu/bolo Local Government Area, Rivers State

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Abstract

This study examined anxiety as correlate of academic performance among secondary school students in Ogu/Bolo local government area of Rivers State. Correlational design was employed in the study. The population of the study comprising students from Government Secondary School, Ogu., Government Technical College, Ele-Ogu and Community Secondary School, Bolo in Ogu/Bolo LGA. Cluster sampling technique and simple random sampling technique were used to select 400 respondents from the population. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire designed to measure anxiety in students. Based on the results, obtained it was revealed that there is a significant negative relationship between test anxiety, cognitive anxiety and academic achievement of secondary school students in Ogu/Bolo local government Area. Secondly, weak positive relationship exists between social anxiety and academic performance of secondary schools. The researcher therefore recommends that the conditions under which these tools are administered should be treat-free but socially bias (the learner can face his/her reality with a relaxed mind-set).

Keywords: *Anxiety, Correlate, Academic Performance, students.*

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is a complicated psychological problem even among students of all ages, but for the purpose of this study we shall narrow it down to secondary school students. Anxiety is high each time we talk of test and examination writing or parental expectations or success in life endeavor. Anxiety can affect a student cognitive abilities or behavioral situations or psychological states (Zeidner, 2014). Anxiety produces a disorder if consistently been experienced in life, thereby leading to common mental health conditions (even among students in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area) that are unstable.

Generally, in Rivers State, children are trained to acquire knowledge and high score in their academic work through what educationist calls "hard work" (i.e. being engaged in much reading or busy with solutions to assignments). To achieve academic success the students are ready to go extra-mile outside class attendance to school; some still attend evening lessons as part of the educational activities (not minding their age or brain maturation). This gradually doctorates into nervous pressure each time academic exercises on evaluation are being mentioned or carried out within or around these students in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area.

Due to their environmental terrine (Old fishing port settlement turned into a community) that lacks certain quality of teaching staff in the government and community owned secondary school level of education, an unhealthy academic phobia gives rise to success pressure created from psychological stress or tension; especially among the final year students (SS 3 students) who are preparing for their externally modulated exam known as "West African Examination Council (WAEC) exams". This stress builds up into various forms of anxiety within them.

As the examination date draws closer, the anxiety in them wax stronger and turns into emotional pains that exhibits certain level of helplessness, hypertension and mental disorganization as its climax. According to McCready, (2018). Anxiety is a major predictor to academic performance. Some studies in psychology have it that anxiety has a detrimental effect on students if not carefully managed by experts. To them students with high level of anxiety are bound to achieve very low academic success/performance (Chang, Shen, & Wang, 2017).

When anxiety is high in students, it interferes with their level of concentration in the classroom section or memory recall which is critical for academic success (Schunk, & DiBenedetto, 2020). According to Nadeem, Ali, Maqbool, & Zaidi et al (2012) the impact of anxiety on the academic achievement of students (having different mental

abilities) shows a proportional increase each time failure records are announced by the school head (principal). This phobia is currently on the increase within the local government area.

In an environment where cultism creeps from the university environment to the neighboring society/community, nearby secondary schools (as seen in Ogu/Bolo), begins to copy their activities by getting recruited into one fraternity or the other. Students no longer take instructions from their teachers because of the maximum protection these recruiters promise them. Respect for school constituted authorities is no longer invoked; rather cult-students apply treat mechanism to force other peers into joining them in their cultic activities. Refusal to belong will leave such student under fear or emotional torture from anxiety disorder which leads into feeling frightened to attend classes for reasons best known to them.

From interaction with these students the researcher observed that fear of the unknown or sudden attack from other rivalry cult could be imminent. So they had to stay out of class most time or enter any class lesson unnoticed. Should the teacher raises voices of correction, or make any attempt of flogging a member, that day will be hell on earth for such teacher (either on his/her way back home or right inside his/her room). This means both non-cultic students and teachers stay in fear or with the feeling of uneasiness during class section or relaxation situations.

With these activities in the community, if left untreated; anxiety disorder can make it hard for students to go close to school environment with uniforms talk much doing class work or test as an evaluative exercise to study. Let me quickly point our here that it may affect their relationships with fellow peers or teachers. This is seen by the number of time student misses classes or school periods and they could completely avoid school for no concrete reason except common anxiety disorder giving by Shrim (2019) is as follows:

- (a.) Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) – These is one of the characteristic of anxiety that people who have too many things to worry about. It might cut across physical symptoms of headaches, stomach-aches, muscle tension or tiredness.
- (b.) Phobias – A phobia is an intense unrealistic fear of a specific thing like dogs running after them or a sudden appears of snakes or spiders at their seating point, due to negative stories they heard from either peers or friends. A child with phobia will go extra length in avoiding those things that causes fear in them. Sometime religious inclinations, believes or norms can plant phobia into teenagers like secondary school children.
- (c.) Social Anxiety –Is one of the characteristic anxieties that made students to developed fear of being called up in the class to say something or perform one task or another. They are afraid of being judged by either the teacher or his/her class-mates. So students with social anxiety will avoid situations where they may be picked or be seen by a large group of persons as hero or exceptional student.
- (d.) Panic Disorder – these are situations where students have an intense episode of fear based on what they hear about the thing or happenings around the area they live. This could include ways girls are been forcefully raped or stealing habits are high or on the increase or things other cult members does to victims in retaliation of a worst incidence or ritual killers existing within the location or those things that can cause a pounding heart beat or shortness of breath or dizziness at first sight of suspects. Panic attacks can happen unexpectedly.
- (e.) Separation Anxiety – these are situations where parents or care-givers are separated for a long time from their teenager children by reason of divorce or single parenting or very busy work schedule. This separation may be caused by disagreement between couples at home or working condition of service of both parents or care-givers being too money conscious and over demanding and not paying adequate attention to their teenage girls/boys.

From the present educational system in Nigeria, academic achievement is a function of student performance in his/her school work measured by grade report, teachers' observation and self-perception. It is the outcome from these determinants that gives every student and his/her education setting achievable goals. Research data's showed that success in academic achievement increases self-confidence and self-esteem of the student (Azeem, 2018). Anxiety opposes this situation by creating a complicating picture or image of the situation.

Anxiety is an in-build action based human trait that has the ability to destroy or mold an individuals' future career. Anxiety can be triggered by the following factors – *Personal factors* which includes emotional disorder, health

disorder maladjustment, low-self-esteem, low aspiration levels, low intellectual level, etc. (Kaur & Kaur, 2021). Next are *Familial factors* which include low socio-economic status, lack of guidance, indifferent attitude of parents and other family problems (Gautam, 2011).

Following the Nigerian system of education even children in nursery and primary schools are trained to acquire more knowledge and high scores in each subject been taught not minding how many subjects as against brain maturation. As they grow up these children are made to carry extra educational load by attending evening or afternoon lessons either in their respective schools or from a private teacher. This type of pressure creates psychological stress that translates over time into a type of anxiety like panic, helplessness, hypertension and mental disorganization (McCready, 2018).

Academic test anxiety leads to academic difficulties through irrelevant thoughts, preoccupation, which in turn reduces attention & concentration (Caruso, Witkiewitz, Belcourt-Dittloff, & Gottfried, 2001). This because a major cause of poor result recorded for the student by the teachers' evaluation (by the end of the test). When academic anxiety is high, there is always in interference with concentration and memory work which is critical to academic performance (Embse, & Hasson, 2012).

Baro and Mishra, (2022). Found that academic anxiety on adolescent female is affected by their socio-economic status. Singh and Singh, (2014) investigated the effects of socio-economic status and cultural settings on anxiety, frustration and neuroticism on students having different levels of achievements. He found that rural high achievers had more anxiety and neuroticism than urban failures whose anxiety was caused by frustration. Low achievers and failures belong to the middle socio-economic status. Kumar, (2013) found that academic anxiety and home environment of adolescent students correlated significantly.

Statement of the Problem

Students with anxiety disorder shows a passive attitude to studies as found among secondary school students in Ogu/Bolo communities, caused by the lack of interest in learning (which means the teachers are to blame) or poor performance (caused by anxiety) in exams and assignments as a result of one phobias or the other. It is possible that most students in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area may be suffering depression caused by treats from a cultist who matures into anxiety or mental disorder. No one is available to talk to them or listen to their complains or see how to cure anxiety inside of them before they go outside to look for solutions.

According to World Health Organization (WHO, 2019) common mental disorders are increasing all over the world among females than males. Between 1990 to 2013 the number of victims increased from 416 million to 615 million which is about 50% increase and accounts for 30% of the non-fatal anxiety diseases worldwide. Anxiety is a factor associated with school dropout and under-achievement in secondary school students, with 30% of the population showing symptoms of anxiety in the first semesters of a university career (since they were faced with several challenges like choosing a program or a life-partner, learning new concepts or remain and maintain old ideas, adapting to groups or peers demand, passing exams through the use of an alternative means or planning a money generating activities within secondary or university levels (Arco, Lopez, Heilborn, & Fernandez, 2005).

From different studies, it was reported that change process in teenagers or secondary school students causes stress period which makes boys to be more stubborn and girls disobedient to parental directives. For some teenagers in secondary school, the stress changes them positively with an effect that stimulates and motivates them into becoming vulnerable to both physical and mental alertness (Arco, et al 2005).

This study shall deal with the challenges that cause these changes and how they can be turned towards improving academic performance by enhancing all learning difficulties. Anxiety can be changed or turned increasingly into a useful tool for academic success among secondary schools students; but if not properly checked or handled, it can equally turn the student who is a victim into a beast. The underlying assumption for this study is that "anxiety can be used to control evaluative tools for competence elevation rather than something that threatens emotions with negative consequences".

According to Arunachalam (2010) India is the most populated country in the world with too much of rush or being in a hurry in every field of endeavor due to the high level of competition among citizens. India's educational system is the third largest in the world, yet the nation suffers from a crippling quantity and quality of education. When this hindrance was unbearable to their children and students, it leads to maladjustment, anxious about their educational outputs (Markovic, & Bowker, 2017). Anxiety here was seen as an emotion based on the appraisal from treats generated from the unhealthy competition (which are symbolic, anticipatory/uncertain elements). Anxiety resulted when cognitive system no longer relate with the real world around them. Anxiety was the reason why student feelings of helplessness gave birth to failure, so that those who suffered from anxiety avoided classroom delivery (Saraso, (2013). Consequently, in our society today if anxiety is not addressed fast it could lead to consequences like irritability, insomnia, impulsivity, isolation and impotency (The New Indian Express, 2014).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship which exists between anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area, Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to

1. examine the relationship between test anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State.
2. Investigate the relationship between cognitive anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State
3. Determine the relationship between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State

Research Questions

The following questions was developed by the researcher as a guide to the study

1. What is the relationship between test anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between cognitive anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study and was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?
2. There is no significant relationship between cognitive anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?
3. There is no significant relationship between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The research design used for this study is correlation research design. According to Nwankwo (2013) whenever a researcher is interested in finding the relationship between two or more variables, such is a correlation study. This study is concerned with establishing the relationship between anxiety and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ogu/Bolo local government Area of River State.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Ogu/Bolo local government area, one of the 23 local government areas in Rivers State with her headquarter at Ogu community. Ogu/Bolo is a Local Government containing two major communities joined together. The LGA has three major schools namely, Government Secondary School, Ogu,

Government Technical College, Ele-Ogu (a public junior and senior secondary school located at Chuku-Ama, Ogu), Community Secondary School, Bolo. With the outbreak of cultism from the city boys, the area began to experience serious recruitment of students into various fraternities as a way of expanding their membership. This factor drew the researchers' interest into investigating the kind of anxiety created by intimidation used as a weapon of recruitment, not minding the student's emotional and academic achievements or prospects.

Population of the Study

The population of the study involved all the senior secondary school students in Ogu/bolo local government Area of Rivers State. Available statistics revealed that there were three thousand nine hundred and ninety six (3996) senior secondary school students in the secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo local government Area of Rivers State.

Sampling and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of the study was 400 senior secondary school students. This was obtained through Taro Yamene formular (1967) which gave a minimum sample size of 364. Sample selection was done using cluster random sampling technique. Fifty (50) students were selected from 8 secondary schools across the Ogu/Bolo local government area. Hence, the total respondents used for this study was 400

Instrument for Data Collection

Two instruments were used in the study. One was an instrument obtaining information on the academic performance of students in their subjects. The instrument was titled "Students' Academic Performance Scale (SAPS)". The instruments contain 15 items measuring the academic performance of the respondents. The second instrument for collection of data was a self-constructed questionnaire titled "Anxiety Measuring Scale (AMS)". The instrument was designed in three sections and each of the sections has 10 items. Each section contains items that measures test anxiety, cognitive anxiety and social anxiety. In total the number of items consisted in the instrument was 30 items. The responses followed the 4-point response scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and strongly Disagree (SD), developed with a large pool of positive and negatively keyed items for both variables. The respondents are expected to tick the degree to which they accept or disapprove the items. The scoring was done as follows SA - 4 points, A - 3 points, D - 2 points and SD - 1 point for all positive items while negative items were scored as follow: SA -1 points, A -2 points, D -3 points and SD -4 point respectively. The higher the response score of a student in the instrument, the higher their level of anxiety display in each of the areas of anxiety considered in this study. The highest possible point for each section was 120 while the minimum was 30.

Validity of the Instrument

The instruments were face and content validated by the researchers' supervisor and two other experts from the department of Educational Measurement and Evaluation. These experts ascertained the fact that the instrument can measure what it is supposed to measure. According to Asuru (2015), face validity is the degree to which an item intends on its face value looks relevant, reasonable and appropriate as a measure of what the item intend to measure. While the content validity is the systematic examination of items to determine the degree to which the content covers a representative sample of the subject matter. Thus the instrument was vetted in terms of language structure, relevancy and its appropriateness while in use. The corrections were effected before it was finally administered to the respondents (senior students).

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument determined through a test-retest method for a measure of stability in its result. Simple random sampling was used to draw a sample sage from different schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Areas. Copies of the instrument were administered on them and after an interval of two weeks the same instrument was re-administered to the same group. All the weakness observed in the instrument was addressed, so that the initial and final test on the retrieved instrument results was collated and computed using Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient (δ). The reliability coefficient indexes obtained were 0.88 and 0.72 for both APS and AMS respectively which was considered reliable.

Administration of Instrument

Instruments were administered directly to the students in their respective schools with the aid of a research assistant. The instruments were administered to the students after giving uniform instructions. The instruments were collected on the spot to ensure maximum retrieval of distributed questionnaire. At the end of the exercise, only 374 copies were retrieved.

Method of Data Analysis

The complete instrument was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation while the hypotheses were tested statistically using t-transformation formula. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The decision is that if the calculated value of t (t-cal) is less than the critical value of t (t-crit), the hypothesis was accepted but if the calculated value of t (t-cal) is greater than the critical value of t (t-crit), the hypothesis was rejected.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between test anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?

Table 1: PPMCC between test anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools

Variables	N	ΣX ΣY	ΣX^2 ΣY^2	Σxy	R	Remarks
Test Anxiety(X)	374	1355.15	3389.38	4012.06	-0.71	High negative relationship
Academic performance (Y)	374	1644.31	4876.93			

Field Survey data, 2022

Table 1 presents the Pearson’s product moment correlation coefficient between test anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/bolo Local Government, Rivers State. The analysis revealed that the r-value or correlation coefficient obtained was -0.71. This value indicated that there is a negative strong correlation between test anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/bolo Local Government, Rivers State. This implies that the more a student’s possess anxiety for test and examination the more their academic performance reduces.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between cognitive anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?

Table 2: PPMCC between cognitive anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools

Variables	N	ΣX ΣY	ΣX^2 ΣY^2	Σxy	R	Remarks
Cognitive Anxiety (X)	374	2301.13	4351.35	4134.07	-0.51	Moderate Negative relationship
Academic performance (Y)	374	1237.05	4211.01			

Field survey, 2022

Table 2 presents the Pearson’s product moment correlation coefficient between cognitive anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/bolo Local Government, Rivers State. The analysis revealed that the r-value or correlation coefficient obtained was -0.51. This value indicated that there is a negative moderate correlation between test anxiety and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/bolo Local Government, Rivers State. This implies that the cognitive anxiety of students’ explain the reason for students’ poor performance in their academic activities.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?

Table 3: PPMCC between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools

Variables	N	ΣX ΣY	ΣX^2 ΣY^2	Σxy	R	Remarks
Social Anxiety (X)	374	20055.15	36453.38	6338.36	0.17	Low positive relationship
Academic performance (Y)	374	32284.31	34676.93			

Field survey, 2022

Table 3 presents the Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/bolo Local Government, Rivers State. The analysis revealed that the r-value or correlation coefficient obtained was 0.17. This value indicated that there is a positive low correlation between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/bolo Local Government, Rivers State. This implies that the social anxiety of students' has a low linkage with students' academic performance on a positive side

Test of Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?

Table 4: Test of significance of correlation between test anxiety and students' academic performance

Variable	N	R	t- calc.	t- crit.	Level of significance	Decision
(X)	374	-0.71	34.204	1.960	0.05	Reject Ho
(Y)	374					

Research Data Output

Table 4 shows the test of significance of correlation between test anxiety and students' academic performance. From table 4 the r value was -0.71 and transformed to t-cal value of 34.204 at 0.05 level of significance the t-critical value was 1.96. Since the t-cal value is greater than the t-crit ($t\text{-cal } (34.204) > t\text{-crit } (1.96)$), the hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies than the correlation coefficient was not dues to chance or error. There is a significant relationship between test anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State

There is no significant relationship between cognitive anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State

Table 5: Test of significance of correlation between cognitive anxiety and students' academic performance

Variable	N	R	t- calc.	t- crit.	Level of significance	Decision
(X)	374	-0.51	14.211	1.960	0.05	Reject Ho
(Y)	374					

Research Data Output, 2022

Table 5 shows the test of significance of correlation between cognitive anxiety and students' academic performance. From table 4 the r value was -0.71 and transformed to t-cal value of 14.211 at 0.05 level of significance the t-critical value was 1.96. Since the t-cal value is greater than the t-crit ($t\text{-cal } 14.211 > t\text{-crit } (1.96)$), the hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies than the correlation coefficient was not dues to chance or error. There is a significant relationship between cognitive anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State

There is no significant relationship between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State?

Table 6: Test of significance of correlation between social anxiety and students' academic performance

Variable	N	R	t _{-calc.}	t _{-crit.}	Level of significance	Decision
(X)	374	0.17	4.350	1.960	0.05	Reject Ho
(Y)	374					

Research Data Output, 2022

Table 6 shows the test of significance of correlation between social anxiety and students' academic performance. From table 4 the r value was 0.17 and transformed to t-cal value of 4.35 at 0.05 level of significance the t-critical value was 1.96. Since the t-cal value is greater than the t-crit ($t\text{-cal } 4.35 > t\text{-crit } (1.96)$), the hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies that the correlation coefficient was not due to chance or error. There is a significant relationship between social anxiety and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area Rivers State

Discussion of Findings

The result from question one of this study showed that there is a strong negative relationship between test anxiety and academic performance of secondary school students in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The hypothesis showed that the relationship was not due to chances that there is a significant negative relationship between test anxiety and academic performance of students. This is in agreement with Goleman (2017) findings that experience is not isolated but connected to previous opportunities of learning that associated with emotions. The cognitive manifestation herein presented as academic performance defines the behavior can only drive through emotional platforms designed by test and examinations as to quacking decision makings.

From the results of question two revealed that there is a moderate negative relationship between cognitive anxiety and student's academic performance among secondary school students in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area. The hypothesis implied that the relationship was not due to chances, that is there is a significant negative relationship between cognitive anxiety and academic performance of students This result supports Dirks (2006) conclusion that society makes a man by shaping his experiences based on the environmental conditions or factors facing the individual. Emotions are healed by closed peers or friends (which include classmates) who do proffer solutions to a common problem facing their friend. Hence the presence of these individuals can either impede or motivate learning in the life of the student.

Results from the third question showed that there is a weak positive relationship between social anxiety and students' academic performance among secondary school students in Ogu/Bolo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The hypothesis showed that the relationship was not due to chances, that there is a significant positive relationship between social anxiety and academic performance of students this supports Opengart (2005) findings that cognitively speaking, emotions define phobia which in turn causes the brain to recognize or alter a thinking pattern so as to affect learning experiences positively or negatively. Poor engagement of a student emotion will definitely cause an increase in phobia towards that evaluative tool and failure becomes ultimate outcome.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings it was concluded that anxiety among students exhibits in diverse forms, which are test anxiety, cognitive anxiety and social anxiety. The conclusion of the research in specific revealed that there is a strong negative relationship between test anxiety and students' academic performance. Also, weak negative relationship exists between cognitive anxiety and academic performance of senior secondary school students. Lastly, positive weak relationship occurs between social anxiety and students' academic performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should pre-inform students about the test or exams in a friendlier manner that is free from any form of treat or intimidation. This will help eliminated or reduces phobia for this teachers' evaluative tool.
2. While administering a test or exam, the learner should be given enough time like in the case of assignments and they should be placed in a comfortable situation free from all forms of psychological restrictions or any conditions that may make him/her feeling inferior in the exam or test hall.
3. Each level of learners should be giving basic admission orientation on how test or exams will be administered in the school and what they stand to loss for not taking part in it.
4. Parents should try not to talk their children into hating certain subjects for one reason or the other. These children needs encouragement, support and positive information's that bring out their best academically.
5. All the learner needs is effective communication between the teacher who the examiner and the style or nature of questioning. If they get used to a teachers style of questions, the lesser their anxiety towards success or failure.

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